

Laser-modified wire arc cladding

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Wire arc cladding
Cobalt alloy
Laser oscillation
Preheating
Cooling rate
Microhardness
Microstructure

ABSTRACT

The deposition of functional cladding layers is a widely adopted technique to enhance the surface performance of engineering components without compromising their bulk material properties. Among the available techniques, wire arc cladding offers high productivity and is particularly effective for depositing relatively thick coatings. Thanks to its high hardness and reasonable toughness, Stellite 6 alloy is well-suited for wear-resistant claddings; however, its application through various welding processes is often accompanied by cracking. In this study, we propose and experimentally investigate a novel approach to wire arc cladding of this Co-based alloy that integrates localized in-situ heat treatment using a defocused oscillating laser beam. The laser-assisted process produced continuous and more uniform cladding layers. Compared to conventional wire arc cladding, the cooling rate decreased by 40 %, resulting in improved bead homogenization and fewer welding voids, while maintaining comparable microhardness after two passes. Enhanced bead fusion, facilitated by the laser, enabled very high deposition speed without compromising the structural integrity of the claddings.

Introduction

Deposition of functional cladding layers is a widely adopted technique to enhance surface performance and thereby extend the service life of components, without compromising their bulk material characteristics (Huang et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2021; Przystupa, 2023; Sathish et al., 2021). Moreover, it provides an effective means of achieving superior properties in massive components without incurring the high costs associated with using bulk advanced materials. Among the various cladding techniques, wire arc cladding is a highly productive process well-suited for depositing relatively thick layers (Iqbal et al., 2025). The process, which utilizes the technology of gas metal arc welding (GMAW), employs the heat of the arc to melt the filler wire and the surface layer of a component (substrate), thereby forming a bead. Thus, a dilution of filler with substrate is always present and typically reaches 20–40 % for this technology (Giudice et al., 2024, Nouri et al., 2007). To minimize dilution, low-heat-input regimes of the arc source are used (Pickin et al., 2011; Rajeev et al., 2019). If necessary, the dilution can be further reduced by multi-pass cladding (Emami and Elahi, 2024; Matias et al., May 2022), ensuring the required chemical composition of the surface cladding layer.

Cobalt-based alloys exhibit an excellent combination of metallurgical and mechanical properties, which they retain even at elevated temperatures. Co-based enhancing claddings find applications in engine parts, drilling tools, poppet and gate valves, valve seats, pump shafts and bearings, erosion shields, acid-resistant machine tools, etc. to increase corrosion- and wear-resistance of these components (Apay and Gulenc, 2014; Birol, 2010; Cinca et al., 2013; Daniel et al., 2023; Falqueto et al., 2017; Kapoor et al., 2012; Lin and Chen, 2006). Thanks to its high hardness at reasonable toughness, Stellite 6 is the most widely used cobalt-based alloy for cladding applications. However, it can be challenging to apply without cracking in the welded form.

Wire arc manufacturing processes often encounter typical issues, such as poor homogenization, lack of fusion, or pores (Chaturvedi et al., 2021; Ron et al., 2020; Siddiqui et al., 2025). A very low cladding speed (in units of $\text{mm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) is usually reported to achieve defect-free claddings (Tapiola et al., 2023; Yu et al., 2024). Bead and under-bead cracks may occur, especially when quenched steel substrates are used (Xiong et al., 2019). The hardness of the heat-affected zone (HAZ) in martensitic creep-resistant steel should not exceed 350 HV10 according to the ISO 15614-14:2013 standard. Thus, substrate is often preheated to reduce the cooling rate, resulting in a lower increase in HAZ hardness and lower

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jajp.2026.100381>

residual stress. Otherwise, a post-clad heat treatment may be required to minimize the risk of cracks. However, any additional heat treatment diminishes production efficiency.

Hybrid and combined laser-arc processes are beneficially applied in welding to stabilize the process and reduce cooling rate (Barenji et al., 2025; Huang and Yhang, 2010; Liu et al., 2023; Moradi et al., 2013; Šebestová et al., 2018). Similarly, beam oscillations have been successfully implemented in welding to refine weld microstructure, modify bead geometry, and enhance mechanical properties (Horník et al., 2022; Hu et al., 2022; Šebestová et al., 2024). These approaches have been applied only rarely in cladding applications and typically involve configurations in which the laser acts directly on the arc, thereby forming a shared melt pool (Barroí et al., 2011; Ren et al., 2022) or preheats a filler wire (Ali et al., 2015). In the present study, we combined both approaches and applied them in cobalt-based alloy cladding on creep-resistant steel. Nevertheless, our configuration is fundamentally different, with the laser beam preceding the arc primarily preheating the substrate.

In our research, we introduce and experimentally investigate a novel approach to wire arc cladding of cobalt-based alloy modified by a defocused oscillating laser beam. The aim of the beam utilization is to locally in-situ clean and preheat the substrate, increase deposition stability, and reduce the bead cooling rate, thereby achieving good fusion, a better level of homogenization, and a lower increase in HAZ microhardness at high-speed cladding. An oscillating laser beam was used to accumulate sufficient heat in the substrate prior to the arc pass. The substrate surface was positioned out of the focal plane to achieve a conduction regime without keyhole formation, thereby limiting the depth of penetration. To our knowledge, this approach to the cladding process is unique and has not been previously published.

Materials and methods

Materials and cladding conditions

The Co-based filler wire ALUNOX AX-FD Co6 (ERCCoCr-A, Stellite 6 equiv.) with a diameter of 1.2 mm was used for cladding of creep-resistant steel P92 (X10CrWMoVNB9–2, 1.4901) solid round bar with a diameter of 75 mm that was rinsed with acetone. Table 1 presents the standardized chemical composition of both alloys.

The TPS 320i MIG/MAG source with WF60i Robacta Drive wire feeder (both from Fronius) was used in Cold Metal Transfer (CMT) regime as a heat source to melt the wire feedstock. The IPG laser YLS-6000 was employed to provide substrate cleaning and preheating. We developed a special hybrid welding/cladding head based on IPG FLW-D30-W, combining both heat sources. The ABB IRB 2400 robot with the hybrid head attached and the ABB IRBP A250 rotatory positioner of the substrate were used to produce helical beads with a 3 mm pitch on the round bar. The laser beam with a power of 2.5 kW was perpendicular to the substrate surface and circularly oscillated with a diameter of 3.2 mm to match the bead width. The oscillation frequency was 300 Hz, i.e., close to the maximum limit of galvoscaners for the chosen diameter of circular oscillation mode. The laser beam was delivered via an optical fiber with a 0.1 mm diameter. The collimation lens and the focusing lens had focal lengths of 100 mm and 200 mm, respectively. This configuration resulted in a focal spot diameter of about 0.2 mm. Due to the beam's high power density and relatively large oscillation diameter,

such a small spot size would produce a ring-shaped energy distribution across the affected width of a substrate rather than the desired uniform circular distribution. Therefore, the focal plane was distanced to achieve a spot of 4 mm in diameter on the substrate surface. Fig. 1 presents the difference in moving trajectory histograms (characterizing power distribution across the affected width) for beam diameters of 0.2 mm and 4 mm, calculated according to (Hu et al., 2022).

The torch's inclination angle relative to the beam was 30°. The beam-to-electrode distance (BED) was set to 6 mm, the minimum permitted by the experimental setup to prevent the laser beam from impinging on the MIG nozzle. Simultaneously, it was sufficiently large to avoid a hybrid process in which both heat sources act in the same melt pool. The offset of 15 mm was applied to prevent molten metal drop leakage. The experimental setup is in Fig. 2. The combination of processing parameters was selected based on preliminary experiments to ensure sufficient heat accumulation without deep laser penetration.

The one-, two-, and three-pass cladding samples were produced with arc parameters summarized in Table 2. The first pass was made with decreased power to limit substrate penetration depth and reduce the dilution. Due to the complexity of the CMT regime, the arc power is not a simple product of electric current and voltage. It continuously changes as high-current and low-current phases take turns, and the average power is predicted by the heat source. The peripheral speed of the substrate was 30 mm·s⁻¹. Pure argon flowing through the MIG torch (18 l·min⁻¹) prevented melt pool oxidation. Using the same setup with the laser switched off, the MIG cladding was performed as a reference.

Methods of process and weld inspection

The cladding process was monitored using the SWIR thermal camera XIR 1800 from XIRIS, which has a resolution of 640 pixels × 512 pixels at 100 frames per second. The camera was positioned as shown in Fig. 4 to monitor the temperature field of the beads after deposition. After the cladding, the thermal cycles at axial points (3 px × 3 px) on the third bead's surfaces were extracted from thermal data. The cooling rates in the temperature ranges 1200–800 °C (CR_{12/8}), 1000–800 °C (CR_{10/8}), and 800–500 °C (CR_{8/5}) were conventionally calculated.

Polished bead cross-sections were etched with Vilella Bain reagent for 12 s to reveal the macro and microstructure of the substrate. The microstructure of the claddings was revealed by electrolytical etching in Lucas reagent at 1 V for 1 s. The samples were examined using a Keyence VK-X1000 laser scanning confocal microscope and a FEI Magellan 400 scanning electron microscope with AMETEK EDAX Octane Elect Super EDS detector. The EDS measurements were performed at 20 kV and 3.2 nA at a dwell time of 50 ms. The spacing of EDS linear measurements was 0.1 mm. ImageJ software was used to binarize microstructural images and quantify the eutectic phase fraction of individual cladding layers.

The dilution D was calculated based on the cross-sectional areas, using the formula shown in Fig. 3.

Vickers microhardness was measured using a hardness tester, Qness 60 A+ EVO, at a load of 100 g. The indents were spaced at 0.1 mm intervals in linear measurements, and the hardness maps were generated with a grid spacing of 1 mm × 0.25 mm. The average microhardness of the last layer was calculated using indentation data within the layer's minimum depth across all beads of the layer. A load of 10 kg was applied for measurements in the HAZ, where the indents were positioned

Table 1

Chemical composition of experimental alloys in wt. %.

Material	Co	Cr	Ni	W	Si	C	Mn	Fe	Mo	Al	Ti	V	Nb	B	N
ERCCoCr-A	Bal.	25–32	< 3	3.0–6.0	< 2	0.7–1.4	< 2	< 5	< 1						
P92		8.5–9.5	< 0.4	1.5–2.0	< 0.5	0.07–0.13	0.3–0.6	Bal.	0.3–0.6	< 0.02	< 0.01	0.15–0.25	0.04–0.09	0.001–0.006	0.03–0.07

Fig. 1. Static trajectory, moving trajectory, and moving trajectory histogram for beam diameters of 0.2 mm and 4 mm (circular oscillation with a diameter of 3.2 mm and frequency of 300 Hz at welding speed 30 mm·s⁻¹).

Fig. 2. The schemes of the experimental setup showing the arrangement of heat sources and measurement equipment, and an example of an image captured during the cladding process.

Table 2
Arc source processing parameters.

Pass	Feeding rate [m·min ⁻¹]	Current [A]	Voltage [V]	Power [kW]
1	8.0	196	15.6	3.5
2 and 3	11.6	270	17.4	5.1

between the map indents spaced about 0.2 mm from the fusion line. These measurements met the requirements of EN ISO 9015–1.

Experimental results

Effect of laser beam impact on the substrate

First, the impact of the beam itself was examined. The temperature field induced by the oscillating beam on the substrate surface, along with the line profiles of temperature perpendicular to the deposition direction (transversal profiles), is shown in Fig. 4. The profile labeled "laser" represents the region of the incident beam. The second transversal profile is located 6 mm away, corresponding to the BED. The axial profile depicts cooling along the deposition direction within a 17 mm-long region following beam impact. It is evident that the beam not only preheats the surface but also melts it. However, the substrate surface rapidly cools after the beam passes since the volume of the substrate

Fig. 3. The scheme of multi-bead cladding with the formula for dilution D calculation.

Fig. 4. The temperature field induced by the laser and the temperature profiles on the substrate surface.

is substantially larger than the region of beam impact. In the BED, the substrate temperature reaches about 800 °C.

Fig. 5 shows the cross-section of four overlapping remelted beads induced by laser beam passes without a filler wire, the corresponding

map of microhardness and microstructures observed in the substrate, HAZ, and fusion zone. The total average width of 4 tracks is (15.6 ± 0.1) mm. Based on the thermal data, the $CR_{8/5}$ reaches a rate of $720 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, resulting in a martensitic microstructure. The beam quenches the

Fig. 5. The macrostructure of overlapping layers remelted by laser (top left), the corresponding map of microhardness (bottom left), and the microstructure of individual zones with detailed microhardness profile (right).

substrate up to 600 HV0.1, while the substrate's original average microhardness was (244 ± 9) HV0.1. The depth of the remelted quenched layer is approximately 0.3 mm, and together with the HAZ, they do not exceed 1 mm.

Laser-MIG vs MIG cladding

The comparison of MIG and laser-MIG macrographs is in Fig. 6. The total average width of 4 partially overlapping beads with 3 mm pitch was (15.1 ± 0.9) mm and (16.8 ± 0.5) mm for MIG and laser-MIG, respectively. During the first pass, the MIG process failed to produce a continuous cladding layer due to poor fusion between adjacent beads. This was caused by a high wetting angle resulting from excessive cladding speed, which limited energy transfer to the substrate. Generally, more welding defects appeared in the MIG cladding layers, especially at the interface of beads and the bead-substrate interface. Laser implementation resulted in a deeper both fusion zone and HAZ of laser-MIG compared to MIG cladding, and produced continuous, more uniform cladding layers with lower porosity and improved fusion. On the other hand, the dilution of laser-MIG was higher than the dilution of MIG claddings. The most significant difference was detected in the first pass (26 % vs. 14 %). The second (third) pass resulted in dilution of 8 % (4 %) and 1.2 % (0.3 %) for laser-MIG and MIG, respectively.

The chemical composition of the three-pass laser-MIG cladding layer was examined with EDS along the yellow dotted line marked in the bottom right image in Fig. 6. The EDS weight data and corresponding microstructures are in Fig. 7. The bead's microstructure is primarily composed of Co-based solid solution matrix, while the interdendritic regions are occupied by eutectics rich in chromium carbides. The fraction of eutectic phase was 22 %, 32 %, and 33 % in the first, second, and third cladding layer, respectively. The first pass induced a relatively large dilution characterized by approximately 20 % of iron in the bead. The higher portion of iron in the cobalt-based alloy reduced the portion of the eutectic phase rich in carbides. Thus, a lower microhardness can be expected in the first pass. The following passes compensated for the dilution and achieved the composition prescribed for ERCCoCr-A.

Fig. 8 presents Vickers microhardness maps measured on polished cross-sections. The average microhardness values of the last (surface) layer after one, two, and three passes are presented in Table 3. In the first pass, the average microhardness of the laser-MIG claddings was 13 % lower compared to MIG, which corresponds to a higher level of dilution caused by the generally higher heat input. As mentioned above, with an increasing number of passes, the dilution differences decrease, and comparable microhardness averages are achieved for the corresponding layers in both technologies. The differences in average microhardness

between the second and third layers are lower than the standard deviations measured within each layer.

Additionally, Vickers hardness was measured in the HAZ close to the fusion line. The positions of these indents in MIG three-pass cladding are visible in Fig. 8. The average values were (409 ± 32) HV10 and (443 ± 20) HV10 for the HAZ of MIG and laser-MIG claddings, respectively. The difference in hardness between the two methods is not meaningful, as the overlap of their uncertainty intervals indicates that the variation lies within experimental error.

Although the HAZ exhibits slightly higher hardness, a slower cooling was observed in laser-MIG cladding. The cooling curves of thermal cycles of MIG and laser-MIG claddings, together with calculated cooling rates, are presented in Fig. 9. Laser implementation reduced the cooling rate in all temperature ranges compared to MIG claddings. However, the most significant decrease of 40 % was observed in $CR_{8/5}$.

Discussion

Speed is a key parameter for the productivity of a cladding process. However, the high cladding speed is often an issue since it supports arc instability. MIG claddings produced at $30 \text{ mm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ were discontinuous and had poor overlap of neighboring beads in the first pass. Higher heat input in the second pass improved the fusion. However, welding voids, such as a lack of fusion or pores, remained in the first-pass layer, and inhomogeneities rich in wolfram were present throughout all layers. The implementation of an oscillating laser beam significantly improved the fusion of neighboring beads. The laser beam in-situ cleaned and pre-heated the substrate surface, partially interfering with the melt pool. Laser-MIG produced wider beads with better overlap, resulting in a smoother surface.

Faster solidification is expected to result in a finer microstructure and more refined eutectic carbides, leading to higher hardness, as reported by (Li et al., 2019). In our research, due to the emissivity differences of different states of matter, the thermal camera was positioned to monitor the already solidified bead. Therefore, the solidification rate from the liquid state cannot be determined. In the highest temperature interval investigated, MIG and laser-MIG third layers exhibited comparable cooling rates, consistent with the similar hardness of this layer in both technologies. However, these values may be subject to a large error because extrapolated temperature data were used.

Lower temperature intervals were characterized by a high decrease in cooling rate induced by the laser beam. The most significant difference of -40% was calculated in the temperature range of $800\text{--}500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. A slower cooling of the solid solution in this temperature range is expected to result in higher hardness, as diffusion-dependent precipitation of fine

Fig. 6. Etched cross-sections of MIG and laser-MIG claddings produced with one, two, and three passes. The yellow line represents the position of the EDS line measurement.

Fig. 7. The EDS line scan along the building direction, i.e. across the cladding layers (position marked with a yellow dotted line in Fig. 6), and the microstructure of individual layers with indents.

Fig. 8. Vickers microhardness maps of MIG and laser-MIG claddings produced with one, two, and three passes. The scale is the same for all cross-sections.

Table 3
Average microhardness of the last layers and corresponding standard deviation.

Pass	MIG	Laser-MIG
1	512 ± 28	448 ± 26
2	539 ± 28	526 ± 26
3	546 ± 36	531 ± 30

secondary carbides can occur over a longer period (Yang et al., 2019). However, this was not observed and laser-MIG claddings had similar microhardness to MIG after two passes. Although infrared thermal imaging provides valuable information on the thermal history of weld

surfaces, it should be recognized that the technique inherently measures only surface temperature distributions and does not capture the temperature field within the liquid melt pool. Cooling conditions within the melt pool may not correspond directly to those observed at the surface, and the microstructural development and resulting hardness may differ. Nevertheless, surface thermal imaging remains useful for assessing relative trends in thermal behavior and for process comparison.

Moreover, differences in the chemical composition of MIG and laser-MIG claddings, resulting from varying levels of filler wire dilution with the substrate, were detected. Laser implementation increased the overall heat input, thereby leading to deeper penetration and, consequently, an undesirable increase in the level of dilution. In the first pass, the dilution

Fig. 9. The cooling curves of thermal cycles measured on the surface of the third bead of MIG and laser-MIG claddings and calculated cooling rates.

of the laser-MIG bead was almost double compared to MIG. The increased content of iron reduced the portion of the eutectic phase rich in carbides and led to lower microhardness of the first pass bead. Nevertheless, in the second pass, the microhardness near the surface was at least 500 HV0.1 for both technologies, which suggests a promising wear resistance of the claddings (Gholipour et al., 2011; Lin et al., 2020; Ratia et al., 2019). The hardness of the cladding is always a result of both its chemical composition and the cooling rate effect, making it difficult to predict.

Slower cooling was supposed to be beneficial for suppressing an increase in HAZ microhardness caused by substrate quenching. Instead, an increase of about 30 HV10 in the average microhardness of the HAZ was observed in the laser-MIG compared to the MIG claddings. However, this difference falls within the standard deviation measured in the HAZ of MIG technology. The 40 % reduction in cooling rate was insufficient to prevent the increase in HAZ microhardness. Based on the continuous cooling diagram of P92 (Peñalba et al., 2010), achieving a 350 HV10 limit of ISO 15,614–14:2013 would require a cooling rate three orders of magnitude slower. ISO 15,614–14 is a mandatory qualification standard primarily applicable in specific industrial laser-hybrid welding procedures, particularly in safety-critical applications where strict control of HAZ is required. In the present study, the aim was not to qualify the procedure according to ISO standards, but rather to investigate the effect of laser assistance on thermal behavior and microstructural evolution in the HAZ. The results demonstrate that our method enables modification of the cooling rate. The magnitude of this effect depends on the overall laser processing parameters and beam characteristics. Nevertheless, cooling rates of a few degrees per second are required to reduce the hardness of P92 steel welds (Ma et al., 2023), which cannot be attained using this method. The potential of HAZ hardness modifications will be further studied on different substrate alloys that are more sensitive to changes in cooling rate.

Nevertheless, the modification of hardness was not the sole objective of this study. The benefits of laser implementation for the cladding structure are indisputable and have been clearly demonstrated. The laser-assisted process enabled very high cladding speed, at which conventional MIG suffered from insufficient bead fusion. Achieving stable arc burning and adequate fusion in the MIG process would require a reduction in cladding speed, which would consequently decrease productivity.

Conclusions

A defocused oscillating laser beam was employed in the wire arc cladding of Co-based alloy on martensitic creep-resistant steel. Based on

the experimental results, the following can be concluded:

- The laser-assisted process is particularly advantageous at high cladding speed, where it produces continuous and more uniform cladding layers with fewer welding voids compared to wire arc cladding.
- Enhanced bead fusion, facilitated by the laser, enabled very high deposition speed ($30\text{mm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) without compromising structural integrity.
- The additional laser heat input reduced the bead cooling rate by approximately 40 %, thereby improving homogenization of the cladding microstructure, while maintaining comparable bead microhardness after two passes.
- The reduction in cooling rate achieved by laser assistance was insufficient to suppress the increase in HAZ microhardness, indicating limited effectiveness for substrate creep-resistant steel HAZ hardness control.
- The hardness of the cladding is influenced by both its chemical composition and thermal history, making it difficult to predict.
- The method is well-suited for high-productivity cladding applications where process stability and fusion quality are critical.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Hana Šebestová: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jan Novotný:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Jan Štěpán:** Resources, Investigation. **Ondřej Ambrož:** Resources, Investigation. **Zdeněk Joska:** Investigation. **Jan Gross:** Resources, Investigation. **Libor Mrňa:** Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This work was co-funded by the European Union and the state budget of the Czech Republic under the project LasApp CZ.02.01.01/00/22.008/0004573. The research infrastructure was funded by the [Czech Academy of Sciences](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17962546) [RVO:68081731]. A part of this work was supported by the Ministry of Defence of the Czech Republic “Long Term Organization Development Plan 1011” – “Military Autonomous and robotic systems” of the Military Faculty of Technology, University of Defence, Czech Republic (Project No DZRO-FVT).

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available. The microstructural images, chemical compositions of individual layers in wt. % measured by EDS, Vickers hardness maps data, and XIR1800 raw thermal images have been uploaded to the Zenodo repository. They are accessible via the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17962546>.

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